

**ANALYSIS OF PROVISION OF SOCIAL BENEFITS UNDER STATE
SOCIAL INSURANCE****D.Sholdarov**

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All the existing countries in the world are going through different stages of formation and development of the social insurance system for social protection of their population, but the requirements for the development of this system are the same, but the problems they arise and the approaches to solving them differ in different levels. The social insurance system remains an integral part of the social policy of these countries. "The development of the social insurance system provides targeted protection mechanisms to the population of the country and, on this basis, serves to ensure socio-economic and financial stability, ensures social harmony and solidarity among the society."¹ In today's rapidly developing world, there are social insurance systems that differ from each other in terms of their components and financing.

The implementation of the social insurance system will certainly require a certain amount of financial resources. Therefore, social funds are an integral part of any economic mechanism. It is known that in order to protect the needy sections of the population, there is a need to redistribute income in a certain order. The financial means of such redistribution is through social funds. Social funds, in turn, can be state or non-state. The ratio between the forms of social savings depends on many factors, first of all, on the national model of economic development.

Social funds are included in the system of financial relations, like any fund, and have a specific financial content. It should be said that at the current stage of world development, the financial system cannot be characterized without a set of social funds, most of which occupy an important place in priority directions. On the other hand, the main purpose of their organization will not be profit.

"Social insurance is intended to solve two main tasks, firstly, to restore and maintain the working capacity of employees, including the implementation of preventive and rehabilitation measures to protect labor and ensure its safe conditions, and secondly, to ensure the financial security of persons who have

lost or do not have the capacity to work aimed at the implementation of guarantee measures”¹.

Ensuring the right of women to use social security in our country, gradually introducing the system of paying pregnancy and childbirth allowances through social insurance in accordance with international standards, as well as the measures of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “Activities on further acceleration of work on the systematic support of families and women” No. PD-87 of March 7, 2022 and “On approval of the strategy of social protection of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan” No. PD-175 of July 25, 2022 were adopted. According to it, on the basis of electronic data received from the “Medical” information system of the Ministry of Health, the information system “Social Protection Single Register” (hereinafter - Appointment and payment by “Single Register” IS) in a “proactive form” without citizens’ appeals, transfer of necessary funds from the Fund to this bank based on allowance payment lists submitted by “Single Register” IS to “National Bank” and payment of benefits by the bank and its departments it is specified that it will be paid to bank plastic cards or in cash².

Social insurance fund is a fund formed at the expense of the State budget and other funds, which does not have the status of a legal entity in the Ministry of Economy and Finance.

A pensioner is a woman who has worked continuously for the last 6 months under an employment contract with a legal entity in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In developed countries, in particular, in Germany, the social protection system is organized on the basis of social insurance, and insurance protection of workers against this type of risk is carried out by institutions of the mandatory insurance system against industrial accidents. These institutions not only provide compensation to those injured in production, but also help in the organization of treatment and rehabilitation services. In Great Britain, the protection of workers against such social risks relies on a corporate insurance system based on private insurance. Insurance compensation for occupational diseases is paid from the state budget through the health care system³.

Estimates of income and expenses of the fund are made based on the forecast of the funds expected to be received in the next year and the expected

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“On measures to develop the state social insurance system”.

“Development of social insurance is an important factor of social protection of the population”. Magazine of “Education News: Research in the 21st Century”. No. 15, part 1 2023.

implementation of expenses for pregnancy and childbirth allowances in the current year. Forecasts of the Fund’s income and expenses for the coming year by sources and expenditure lines are developed by the Ministry of Economy and Finance. Expenditures from the funds of the fund are carried out in accordance with the income and expenditure estimates approved and registered by the director of the responsible department of the Ministry of Economy and Finance.

Figure 1. Funds of the Social Insurance Fund⁴

The unemployment certificate issued in accordance with the procedure for the appointment of the pension is the basis for the appointment and payment of the pension. Within 5 working days from the date of issuing the form of incapacity for work, the information contained in it is entered into the “Medical” information system of the Ministry of Health by the responsible employee of the regional outpatient polyclinic or maternity institution. “Medical” IS will check the information automatically on the basis of the information received through the “Electronic Government” interdepartmental integration platform. When calculating the pensioner’s continuous work experience for the last 6 months, 6 months of continuous work experience up to the date of issuance of the disability certificate in legal entities, except for budget organizations of the “UNLS” ISHC, are taken into account.

⁴“On measures to develop the state social insurance system”.

An indiscriminate payment of funds from the appropriate budget funds for pensions is earmarked funds. Some of them are appointed due to the non-existence of the source of income for various reasons, while others are appointed for the purpose of social protection of needy layers of citizens. Benefits in the first case include benefits paid for temporary disability, pregnancy and childbirth, unemployment and other similar cases. The second type includes one-time payments to women and children, allowances for families engaged in child care, funeral allowances and other payments according to purpose.

The priorities of expanding the coverage of the population by social insurance mechanisms, social and material support of low-income families and material support of persons with disabilities, in particular, the implementation of a unified state policy in the social insurance system, the involvement of the able-bodied population in the social insurance system we propose to introduce incentive mechanisms, to pay pregnancy and childbirth allowances from the funds of the social insurance fund. As a result, a new management system based on advanced international standards will be introduced in this sector, providing targeted protection of the population by the state, improving the procedure for paying pregnancy and childbirth allowances.

